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'Hard-to-reach' parents: immigrant families' participation in schools and the views of parent association leaders in Spain and the United States

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Abstract

While research about the significance of parent participation in school is expanding, research about the role of Parent Associations (PA)/Parent and Teacher Associations (PTA) in the integration and participation of immigrant families in schools is limited. This is still the case in Spain and the U.S. despite the continued growth of the immigrant population and that of a scholarship linking parental involvement in school with the improved educational outcomes of their children. This study explores the role of PA/PTAs leaders in the school integration and participation of immigrant families, many of whom are considered 'hard-to-reach.' The objectives are twofold: to contribute new insights with a description of immigrant families' participation in PA/PTAs in two different national contexts; and to bring new insights from the views of PA/PTAs leaders about how to engage and improve the participation of 'hard-to-reach', immigrant families in schools. We compare results derived from in-depth, semi-structured, face-to-face interviews with PA/PTAs leaders in 26 public schools in Granada and New York City. The study yields two main findings: the importance of immigrant families' active participation in the enrichment of schools; and the strategies used by PA/PTAs leaders in the participation and integration of parents in their children's schools.

Keywords

Hard-to-reach' families; immigrant families; parent associations; parent engagement; leadership

Introduction

The role of parents and families¹ in schools has captured the interests of educators and scholars for a long time. We conceptualize that family structures can range from the traditional two-parent, nuclear family to single-headed family units, with the inclusion of extended kin and non-kin caregivers. This inclusive or more holistic approach allows us to examine diverse systems of support in the education of children in both the school and the home environment, and to reduce contradictions, often apparent in the education and socialization of immigrant school children. Both the home and the school environments play a unique yet interrelated role, as both influence the students'

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processes of learning and development. We argue that this holistic approach takes more fully into consideration the characteristics, needs, and contexts of a child's education.

Scholars agree that a positive relationship between parents and their children (Coleman and Glenn 2009) is strongly associated with the children's positive school outcomes (O'Connor and Scott 2007). Parent involvement has been a vital component in public education (Coleman 1988; Jeynes 2014) and linked to increased student learning (Jeynes 2005, 2007). For this reason, schools need to develop constructive relationships with the family, including non-kin caregivers, to maximize the positive impacts of a child's education and socialization.

Earlier research about the effectiveness of parental engagement (Ramírez Castillo and Sola Martínez 2006) demonstrates that, when students are aware of their families' involvement in schools, as for example, in parent associations (PA) or Parent and Teacher Associations (PTA), this awareness alone positively influences their education. As Ramírez Castillo and Sola Martínez found, 'the family has a role in transmitting and being a model of life style, rules, values and social roles' (241). Therefore the participation of the family in their child's education has a strong influence on their socialization and educational success.

The education and international migration literature also suggests that educational institutions face greater challenges educating the children of immigrants and in helping to integrate their 'hard-to-reach' families in their education. Yet immigrant families are more vulnerable to social and institutional isolation and exclusion and their children face school outcomes similar to those of historically racialized, native-born minorities (Crul et al. 2014; Fuentes-Mayorga 2007; Lopez 2002). These vulnerabilities limit the family's participation and the children's access to a quality education and resources. Consequently, scholars have argued that families need to understand the role of schools or that of academic institutions in supporting and providing for their children's education (Boag-Munroe and Evangelou 2012).

However, earlier literature has indicated that it is schools or service providers that are often out of the reach of families (Crozier and Davies 2007; Landy and Menna 2006). Hence, schools have a key role in reaching out to and educating families about their pivotal role in their children's education. Communication between parents and schools is a key factor in the engagement and participation of 'hard-to-reach' immigrant families. Comparative research about the school integration of immigrant children in different national contexts of reception has also argued for the importance of educating families but also schools about the needs of immigrant families as, different school systems expect different degree and forms of family participation (Crul, Schneider, and Lelie 2012).

Extending this literature, we argue that PA/PTAs leadership positions dictate how the parent-school relationship functions, as these leaders are in a privileged position to shape the routes and content of communication between the family and schools. Therefore PA/PTAs leaders must be committed to the fair and equal access of a quality education for all students, and associations must use different strategies in order to encourage and increase the participation of 'hard-to-reach' families (García-Carmona 2014). Lorenzo Delgado conception of leadership is understood as 'the function of invigorating a group or an organization to generate their own growth and the function of a shared project' (2005, 371). A main premise of this leadership

framework is that in a democratic society, institutions must establish systems of mutual collaboration and shared decision-making processes. As such, schools must strive to include the input of parents in the education of their children, as their values and daily life practices can also enrich and diversify the educational curriculum. Hence, the shared leadership model between schools and families advocated by PA/PTAs is the most adequate leadership to follow (García-Carmona 2014).

Our paper contributes new insights into the integration of ‘hard-to-reach’ immigrant families in schools and the role of PA/PTAs in the school systems of New York City (USA) and Granada (Spain). In the past few decades, these two national contexts have experienced structural and demographic shifts in the share but also diversity of the foreign – and native-born population, and in the availability of school resources. Given the longer legacy of immigration and the larger share of immigrants in New York City, the participation of immigrant families in school is greater (García-Carmona 2014) although it is still a challenge (Cakiroglu 2004). Previous studies have documented the low participation of immigrant parents in the context of Spain (Bueno and Belda 2005; Garreta 2008). Scholars find that increasing immigration and demographic shifts in both national contexts have also challenged schools to develop new approaches to improve the educational integration of immigrant children and the participation of vulnerable, immigrant families in schools (Alba and Holdaway 2014; Fuentes-Mayorga 2012; García-Carmona 2011).

In understanding the barriers faced by immigrant families, scholars have argued that beyond contextual factors, individual factors (such as lack of jobs, time, understanding and/or ability to communicate in the native, host language, among others) limit these families’ participation in schools or in their children’s education (Garreta 1994, 2008). In addition, as most immigrant families live between two different cultures (Olivos 2010), this dual orientation may decrease the ability of parents to understand their roles in the schooling of their children.

We present a twofold analysis of the participation of immigrant families in schools’ PA/PTAs and of the strategies of PA/PTAs leaders in the integration and participation of ‘hard-to-reach’ families in three parts. The first part provides a review of the contributions advanced by the ecological perspective on the engagement of families in schools as well as the characteristics that define ‘hard-to-reach’ immigrant families and parents’ participation in the school PA/PTAs. The second part introduces the main findings of this qualitative study based on insights derived from interviews with PA/PTAs leaders. This allows us to gauge some of the strategies used by PA/PTAs leaders as well as assess the participation of ‘hard-to-reach’ immigrant families in schools’ PA/PTAs. The third and final part describes our analysis of the main findings and their contributions to the study of PA/PTAs, as well as to future educational policies for the engagement and integration of immigrant families in schools.

Theoretical framework of the study: the ecological perspective

To conceptualize family engagement in schools, we start by drawing on the ecological perspective of human development described by Bronfenbrenner (1979). In his early work, Bronfenbrenner considered that five interdependent systems (microsystem, mesosystem, exosystem, macrosystem and chronosystem) combine to shape the

development and education of a child. According to this approach, the family and the school have a principal role in the configuration of the child's microsystem of development. In this framework, the family and the school act as the primary agents in the socialization of school children. Pianta and Walsh (1996) characterized the ecology of schooling as an organized system of interactions and transactions among persons (parents, teachers, students), settings (home, school), and institutions (community, governments) that are oriented to support the developmental and educational progress of students. On the other hand, Lorenzo Delgado (1995, 2011) suggested that the school can be conceived as a social and human ecosystem where different components (population, relationship system, technology and environment) cohabitate and function with the curriculum. From these two perspectives, we can set up the school-family partnership as a space of knowledge exchange and common learning. We frame our analysis with ecological systems models focused on the microsystem development involving the family and the school environment. We conceptualize PA/PTAs as the key mediators between the family and school. However, we explore whether existing ecological frameworks, as those advanced by Bronfenbrenner and others can explain the integration and participation of vulnerable families in schools. These families often lack human and social capital and are not able to understand during the early years of adjustment what the host school system expects of them. We argue that PA/PTAs which include a representative share of immigrant parents and teachers play a key role in socializing these families and facilitating their collaboration within schools. According to Christenson and Reschy (2010), ecological systems theory provides a compelling argument for considering the combined input of the home and the school contexts into the education and development of school children (Bronfenbrenner 1992), drawing attention to relationships and congruence across both contexts, as well as how students utilize their time both inside and outside school (Reschly and Christenson 2009). Overall, we take from ecological systems theories that a child's development is mainly influenced by the collaborative efforts of the family and the school (Bronfenbrenner 1986; Bryk and Schneider 2002; Caspe and Lopez 2006; Christenson 2004; Lawrence-Lightfoot 2003; Murry et al. 2004). The strong relationship among students, family members and the school community has consistently helped students to improve their educational outcomes (Henderson and Berla 1994; Henderson and Mapp 2002).

Thus, in order to get the best learning results possible, families and educational institutions must share tasks and openly communicate about each child's education to achieve the best possible learning results (Christenson 2004; Patrikakou et al. 2005; White 1998, among others). Both institutions must strive to avoid discontinuity between home and school systems, as this creates challenging circumstances for children in terms of communication patterns, expectations, the meaning of learning and effort (Pianta and Walsh 1996). This is a sound reason why scholars should strive to strengthen diverse strategies to reach every family, including 'hard-to-reach,' vulnerable, immigrant families, in the school system, in order to learn about new forms of communication channels for the flow of intercultural education and understanding between the home and the school environment. We find that contrary to expectations, it is schools that often lack the tools and cultural understanding to reach immigrant parents and foster their participation in their children's education; hence why our focus on the mediating role of PA/PTAs.

Immigrant families seen as ‘hard-to-reach’

The educational literature consistently finds that parents have a positive influence on the emotional, behavioural and educational development of their school children. Parental input has proven to be a stronger influence than other factors, such as maternal education, poverty, peers’ socio-economic status and type of schooling (DfES 2003; Desforges and Abouchaar 2003). However, parental engagement is contingent upon many other factors, top among these, being the socio-economic status and parents’ experience with the educational system (Harris and Goodall 2007; Lareau 2003).

Although the definition of ‘hard-to-reach’ groups varies between authors, the term has been applied to members of communities who are eligible for services or programmes but who face challenges with access (Barrett 2008; Brackertz 2007; Coe et al. 2008). According to Evangelou et al. (2013), in the context of engaging families in intervention programmes, ‘hard-to-reach’ families are often described as ‘vulnerable’, ‘isolated’, ‘excluded’ or ‘detached’ from the system.

‘Hard-to-reach’ families face risk factors associated with the lack of resources. These families include but are not limited to members of ethnic, racial or class minorities; or people from immigrant or foreign-born origins; as well as groups who face systemic exclusion due to racial discrimination (Cobas, Duany, and Feagin 2009), including children in families who lack or have limited resources, such as the lack of education or of language skills (Crul et al. 2014). In recent years, comparative studies of the school integration of immigrant children in different national contexts have revealed that parents often lack experience with the host society’s educational system and culture; and that, irrespective of parents’ social class of origin, schools need to understand that different contexts of reception demand different levels of parental participation (Crul, Schneider, and Lelie 2012).

Doherty, Stott, and Kinder (2004) suggested that service providers, in our case schools, need to offer education and also to develop new strategies to help vulnerable or ‘hard to reach’ families participate in their child’s education. A study by Tunstill et al. (2005) suggested that service providers need to ensure that their service-delivery staff members understand the cultural needs and limitations of the families who are part of the institution. Schools need to listen to families to discover their needs. Other scholars have provided specific strategies for how to educate and integrate these families. For example, Crozier and Davies (2007) believed that schools need to find ways to assist the ethnic minorities who lack the privileged knowledge to interpret unspoken expectations in the larger context. Therefore schools that offer bespoke forms of support to these parents (e.g. literacy classes, parenting skill support, regular meetings) are more likely to engage parents of vulnerable backgrounds (Harris and Goodall 2007).

Landy and Menna (2006) believed that ‘working effectively with families who might be labelled “hard-to-reach” involves a shift from perceiving the family as being “hard-to-reach” to thinking about what makes the service that is being offered hard to be procured by a particular family’ (180). For this reason, supporting the capacity for parental participation by immigrant families is of prime interest to schools in improving the educational opportunities of their children, as well as for the rest of the school community.

According to Harris and Goodall (2007), engaging 'hard-to-reach' parents has a disproportionately positive effect on student learning and achievement. Their study reported that, 'where schools have succeeded in engaging these groups of parents, the impact on achievement has been greater than that resulting from the engagement of other groups' (70). Crul et al. (2014) also indicated that both schools and family resources, such as the mentoring provided by older siblings, teachers and community mentoring centres, drive the unexpected educational success of some immigrant children.

Overall, it is also important to include in the ecological models of education and parent engagement an intercultural perspective, one that assumes that both schools and educational institutions can benefit from the cultural resources, strengths and contributions of immigrant families. Therefore we believe that the environment, as well as staff, the student body, families and communities, can improve communication systems that focus on equality and on instilling this value to children from the earliest age possible. These inclusive practices allow the entire school to become enriched and better prepared to offer new forms of learning that is representative of diverse cultures and that prepares future intercultural and global citizens.

Guided by the above literature, we turn our focus to the specific needs of 'hard-to-reach' minority and immigrant families in the school system (Crowley 2005; Glennie et al. 2005; Katz, La Placa, and Hunter 2007). We would like to offer a more inclusive ecological model of family integration in schools through an exploration of the role of PA/PTAs leaders. This model specifically aims at understanding school practices among 'hard-to-reach' families in different national contexts. Research has shown that the lower involvement of language-minority families does not denote a lack of interest in their child's schooling and education. Rather, it reflects a disconnection between the cultural understandings of families and their roles in the education process (Casanova 1996; Crul, Schneider, and Lelie 2012; Gonzalez 1986). We emphasize the need to understand the dual intervention practices of families and schools and the role of PA/PTAs as mediators of this collaborative effort in the education of their children.

Oriented by this literature, the authors of this paper argue that parent association leaders (PA/PTAs), as the main representative entity for parents in the school setting, play a crucial role in mediating family members' involvement.

Parents' participation in the school: the role of parent associations and parent and teachers associations (PA/PTAs) and forms of parent-school engagements

We conceptualize PA/PTAs as both a structure and a mechanism of formal communication between families and schools. According to the U.S. Departments of Health and Human Services (HHS) and Education (ED) (2016, 1), family engagement refers to 'the systematic inclusion of families in activities and programmes that promote children's development, learning, and wellness, including in the planning, development, and evaluation of such activities, programmes, and systems.' Of the various classifications made regarding the forms of engagement and communication between the families and the school (Wylie et al. 2013; Gordon 1977; Lim 2012; Moles 1992; Olivos 2010; Wehlburg 1996), we draw on Méndez Morales's conceptualization (2011) of parent-school engagement that indicated that in schools there are generally two forms of communication with families: a) informal dealings, where

contact is established at the entrance and exit of the school, and b) formal communication, where contact is through meetings in classes and tutorials and through the parent-teacher association. Both types of communication and participation are important, but we consider formal communication, especially by PA/PTAs, a successful tool for the exchange of information between families and schools about students' educational process. Our study documented how PA/PTAs leaders facilitated different channels of parent engagement in their children's schools and education.

According to the New York City Department of Education (Chancellor's Regulation A-660 2012), PA/PTAs are school-based organizations open to the parents of all children attending schools. PA/PTAs are the primary vehicle for parents to meet other parents and teachers; and to learn about the education of their children, and about the needs and resources in their children's schools. This is where parents can share ideas and enrich the school and the larger communities.

PA/PTAs in both the USA and Spain are formed and directed by parent/leaders (executive board) elected by the parents' vote through a democratic procedure. Three common figures appear to compose the PA/PTA, President, Treasurer and Secretary, but they usually work with more members or coordinators in different areas such as ICT (Information and Communication Technologies), community events, cultural tasks, etc. In both national contexts, all PA/PTAs adopt bylaws and hold regular meetings. Their main function is to be part of the decision-making process of the school, in the design of measures that directly affect the education of the community and the setting of guidelines for actions by all families of the school. PA/PTAs also financially support school activities, in addition to helping to get parents involved in school life. They benefit the educational, social and cultural programmes in the school.

Research by Fuentes-Mayorga (2007) indicated how the opportunities provided by the context of reception, as well as by ideologies that exist about different immigrant groups' status, determine the nature of their integration or exclusion in different job sectors and neighbourhood areas of New York City. In our study, we conceived PA/PTAs as spaces where leaders and other parents can mediate the integration of immigrant parents, including those of 'hard to reach' families with few or no educational resources, into the educational system, the community and the larger society. Family-school partnership interventions have placed great emphasis on acknowledging and addressing common barriers to the participation of parents in schools. Some of these barriers have included differences in culture, belief systems, and motivation, and lack of access to resources (Anderson-Butcher 2006; García-Carmona 2014).

This study explored two main questions involving the role of PA/PTAs leaders in the school integration and participation of immigrant families who are considered 'hard-to-reach.' The main questions orienting this study were how is the participation of immigrant families in PA/PTA based on their experiences or agency? And how can schools help immigrant parents to become more involved in their PA/PTA?

Methodology

Design and sample selection

The present study explored the experiences of 26 PA/PTAs leaders with reference to the participation of immigrant families in their school PA/PTA and strategies to increase parental involvement. The participants (5 males and 21 females) were selected within 25 public schools both in New York City, US (11) and in Granada, Spain (14). The sampling of schools in both contexts covered all the elementary school districts in Manhattan (Districts 1, 2, 3, 4, 5 and 6) and in Granada (Albaicín, Beiro, Centro, Chana, Genil, Norte, Ronda, and Zaidín).

In Manhattan the districts with the largest share of foreign-born parents were found in District 6 (with 26.05%) and District 4 (with 16.8%). By contrast, the districts with the lowest shares of foreign-born parents counted were District 3 (with 12.28%) and Districts 1 and 2 (with 13.14% and 13.28% respectively). In Granada districts with the highest presence of foreign-born individuals were the Norte district (with 16.87%) and the Albaicín district (with 15.47%). By contrast, the districts with the lowest presence of foreigners counted were the Genil district (with 5.48%) and the Beiro and Ronda districts (with 7.36% and 7.74% respectively).

Data collection took place over two time periods. The first round of data collection took place in New York City (USA) during spring 2013 before the academic year finished, and the second round took place in Granada (Spain) during the first academic trimester of 2014. Both contexts were selected because both national contexts have experienced in recent decades unprecedented immigration growth. This has increased the share of immigrant students in both educational systems. Also, because New York City has a long tradition educating and integrating immigrant children and their families in parent associations and Granada has a more recent tradition.

As is characteristic of qualitative research designs, the sample selection for the interviews was conducted in using a purposive sampling method (Tójar Hurtado 2006). To understand the role of schools in the integration of immigrant parents in these selected districts, we selected respondents who occupied leadership positions and who participated in school PA/PTAs. We tried to achieve relevance and representation of each leader in different contexts (Granada and New York City) and of the specific reality (districts of each city) that our two research questions addressed.

To ensure the representation of schools in all districts of Granada and New York City, 26 interviews with PA/PTAs leaders were conducted. The sampling selection ended when we reached a theoretical saturation point, when additional interviews no longer provided additional information relevant to our question (Glaser and Strauss 1967).

In this study, the average PA/PTAs leader had between two and eight years of school leadership experience. Only one leader was new to the PA/PTA leadership team and the school environment (with less than two years of experience). The leaders included 21 presidents, 3 secretaries and 2 treasurers. Amongst these, 17 leaders were native born (5 born in New York City and 12 born in Granada) and 9 were foreign-born, or first generation immigrant parents (7 lived in New York City and 2 in Granada). Among these leaders, 5 were men and 21 were women. Each leader was interviewed in his/her school (PA/PTA room), and the majority of the informants were initially contacted through the school principal.

Interviews and procedure

To understand the process of participation of immigrant families in PA/PTAs, and to explore how best to improve the participation of 'hard-to-reach' families in these organizations, we employed a qualitative approach. Data were collected through in-depth, semi-structured face-to-face interviews. We obtained informed consent from all participants prior to the formal interview. Each interview lasted between 45 and 60 minutes. All interviews were conducted in an informal, conversational style that encouraged participants to talk about their PA/PTA leadership experiences in a spirit of collegiality. All personal information that could identify the person was deleted, and each transcript was assigned a code that guaranteed anonymity. All interviews were then recorded and professionally transcribed.

Data analysis

In order to process the interview transcripts, we used a classical content analysis method conducted by earlier scholars (Bardin 1996) for our analytical scheme. This method includes phases of categorisation, text distribution and content analysis. The first step of analysis was identifying the different categories that emerged from the meta-category (the overarching category), 'participation of immigrant families in their school PA/PTA.' We identified five sub-categories involving the two objectives (see Figure 1), as follows: a) Involvement of immigrant families in PA/PTA; b) Recognition of the positive effects or contributions of the participation of immigrant families in the education of students; c) Level of participation of immigrant families in PA/PTA; d) Proposals for the integration of immigrant families into PA/PTA activities; and e) Support for the integration of all families (including immigrant families). The second step of the analysis was driven by the following questions: a) how is the participation of immigrant families in PA/PTA based on their experiences and reflections? and b) How can we help immigrant parents to become more

Figure 1. Analytical schema diagram.

involved in their PA/PTA? This step involved scrutinizing the text passages within each category (e.g. proposals for integration). The third step complemented the analysis of linking the categories with the objectives of the paper to address the general two-folded question leading this study. It involved going back and forth between the original transcript passages to ensure that no relevant aspect had been omitted through paraphrasing and summarising of the interviewees' narratives. These categories were distributed around the two objectives, and subsequently used to organise the findings.

Findings

This section presents an overview of the experiences and perceptions of PA/PTAs leaders around the integration and participation of immigrant families in schools and in the education of their children. The insights also touch upon the aforementioned five larger themes that emerged from the research questions and the two main objectives that guided the analysis of the findings. Because these themes are already well-grounded in the literature about parent involvement (García-Carmona 2014; Garreta 2008; Harris and Goodall 2007; Olivos 2010), our emphasis is on the construction of these themes around the role of PA/PTAs.

The participation of immigrant families in parent associations (Objective 1)

In both the Spanish and the North American educational contexts, PA/PTAs leaders understand that immigrant families' participation has an added, positive effect on the education of their children. New York City itself has a long history of immigration and of educational models to meet the diverse needs of children from different cultures. The public school systems in these national contexts reflect this long legacy of diversity. The PA/PTAs leaders interviewed are aware of the richness of the cultural diversity of their schools and of the benefits that the participation of foreign families brings to the PA/ PTAs and to all students. The involvement of families in the education of their children has been linked with: higher class attendance, grade attainment, and greater overall school performance. The inclusion of parents has also increased the students' awareness about having equal rights in schools. Cultural diversity in the PA/PTA enriches the school as a whole, leading children to engage with and learn more about different cultures and to increase parents' interaction with people of different cultures and languages as well as with different points of views, as the narratives of PA/PTAs leaders revealed:

That diversity in the class also presents itself between the parents, you know. And we do a lot with that, you know. It's fun to be around so many different people that you can expose yourself to languages and cultures. (Interview XXI, District 3, New York City)

Parents know about other cultures and also teach our children that, well, the world is full of different people and we can also learn from each one of those cultures. (Interview XXIV, District 4, New York City)

It has a positive effect; you know. Thanks to the greater diversity and different points of view. How this intercultural model shapes the child is a very important factor in a child's life. (Interview XXV, District 5, New York City)

In Granada, parents who belonged to PA/PTA were aware of the benefits that their participation in this organization offers to all students. They also recognize the positive effects that the involvement of immigrant families entails. They underline that having immigrant families involved increases the acceptance of students, teachers and parents from different cultures and customs; and generates reciprocal exchanges and the enrichment of cultures, and new motivations for 'doing new things,' including increasing diversity of the school's population. The presence of immigrant families from different races and cultures also helps to reduce discrimination, or fear of the unknown and the rapprochement of different cultures. Overall, they contribute to increasing the respect for diverse opinions, and the knowledge pool of school cultures as an *element of helping to improve coexistence*, as the narratives of parents illustrated:

Our children talk a lot about other things. Last year with New Zealand they were impressed with the Maori and the feast of different countries. They discover many things and see that there are other countries, other ways of eating . . . Here, for example, the Muslim community is very integrated. (Interview I, District Albaicín, Granada)

Because if you know Ecuador better, you understand Ecuadorean children better and vice versa, and with everyone, because there are students from everywhere. In my child's class there are Poles, Chinese. My son is an Ethiopian from The Zubia, but he is Ethiopian. There are several Moroccans and South Americans, so I want to say that there is such a vast melting pot of cultures that, if you do not know them, of course, they could not coexist and of course, coexistence is fundamental in education. (Interview XI, District Ronda, Granada)

Consequently, interviews among PA/PTAs leaders suggested that most are committed (in both contexts) to supporting and integrating all families that make up the school, regardless of their origins or roots. Only two PA/PTAs leaders of the 26 included in this study, supporting the integration of foreign families, warned that there are still many prejudices against immigrants in schools, and that the language barrier makes it difficult. The main arguments made supporting the integration of immigrant families varied, but most leaders felt that the participation of any parent is positive, whether the culture is different from or similar to that of the school. These views were summarized in the narratives of leaders, as follows:

Parents at this school view any parent involvement as positive, whether it be a parent from another culture, out of town or both. That does not matter; we're all in this together. (Interview XXV, District 5, New York City)

I think so because of our community. You know, our community is becoming more and more diverse, so I think it's logical for everyone to come to school and see the same thing too. You know that your neighbour is from Africa, that there is someone from Ecuador, Mexico, Puerto Rico . . . It is simply our community in general, so the school will be the same. (Interview XXII, District 4, New York City)

I think so, because if we do not cooperate with all, that is, the education of our children comes first. So, for all this to work, we have to be all, both, those of us that are from here and those from another country together. (Interview VIII, District Norte, Granada)

Regarding 'the participation of immigrant families in their school PA/PTA' overarching category (see [Figure 1](#)), we observed that, in most schools in New York City, leaders point out that, while in some schools there is a good participation by families from

other cultures, in other schools there is a lack of involvement. However, we found that in New York City there is greater participation by immigrant families than in Granada. A few PA/PTAs leaders explained the increasing presence of immigrant parents in their schools and the strategies used to increase their inclusion:

In our PA I would say that it [immigrant parents' participation] is increasing. There is not much, but this year during our book fair. . . we have always sent a package of books in Spanish, and normally we would not have taken them out. But this year, as we have parents whose predominant language is Spanish, we made sure that at least one of them [one book] was there. There was not a moment in our fair where we did not have a parent with Spanish as the predominant language for many reasons, because we had other parents who came and did not speak English and they were our translators. So it is not much, but it is growing slowly. I would say in our events about 10%. We now have more parents from other countries who are participating and, therefore, the participation is growing. (Interview XXII, District 4, New York City)

From the executive board I would say 90% of the members. I have many immigrant parents; we have many immigrant parents. (Interview XXIII, District 4, New York City)

International, they come. The most I can tell you I knew is of seven different countries, and many of us are also involved. (Interview XXVI, District 6, New York City)

However, our discussions with PA/PTAs leaders in Granada highlighted the reality that the participation of foreign-born families in PA/PTAs is still a challenge. In most cases, the participation of immigrant families in an active form is still at minimum levels, although there are schools in which the participation of parents is greater, as was explained by some respondents: 'It depends on the person; it takes time. Different factors stand out because they do not participate; it costs them time away from work; participation depends on the culture. . .'. The insights suggest that immigrant or foreign-born parents with higher education are more involved in the PA/PTAs. It is also noted that there is a low level of participation by both immigrant and native-born families:

It is very difficult. There are a few who do, who integrate a lot, those who are of a "higher" cultural class, maybe people who come to do a thesis and so on. These types of people do tend to get more involved. It is very hard for immigrants, perhaps because of the language, the different culture. . . and it costs them. Over time they end up integrating, but at first it is very hard. (Interview III, District Beiro, Granada)

There are many people from other cultures. It is a school that is completely multicultural. Then they said at first their class is like the UN, there are all ethnic groups, all races and everything. The truth is that we have never had problems. But for the mothers in the PA the truth is that . . . ; the reason I do not know, but there are no immigrant people. I think there is a South American person. I think, I believe and I cannot swear, you know, I think there is not any . . . I would say nobody, but I'm not sure. (Interview XI, District Ronda, Granada)

Helping immigrant families to become more involved in their PA/PTA (Objective 2)

Although in New York City the participation of immigrant families in the PA/PTA was more visible, increasing and also valued, in most cases, educators need to continue to work to encourage the greater participation of families in schools. The insights derived

from parents' interviews and their suggestions provide a series of measures to improve the participation of parents in schools. These are categorised as follows:

- *Languages awareness*: to prepare posters advertising the PA/PTA role in the immigrant students' languages. This is the best way to recruit the participation of diverse and international populations. This should be done in collaboration with translators and the offering of English classes for limited-language families.
- *Attendance*: to increase participation in meetings, offer activities around food, the use of ICT, more information and communication.
- *Cultural Welcoming Environment (CWE)*: to know the languages of the families of the school, to create international groups; celebration of events about the cultures of the school, open dialogue; and to elaborate and use a survey to access the needs, ideas, training courses and teachers' mediation strategies about the inclusion of immigrant parents.

Participants reported that language barriers were the most obvious and important barriers. These must be addressed with the use of translation services, including the availability of bilingual schools, as the following parents suggested:

I think one of the ways would be to work with translations. Last year we had, and was amazing, an organization that came here and helped the school. We talked about the need for translation for the parent-teacher conference, where parents can talk to teachers. They set up a nursery area in the cafeteria and selected one of the members to translate. So we had translation services. Obviously, one of the main languages we found was Spanish; so we had many Spanish translators working, and it was a wonderful help. For this reason, the next conference of the second semester brought many more parents. That is why I believe it is really the translation that helps to integrate the participation of parents who come from other countries. (Interview XXII, District 4, New York City)

Well, we are lucky that this school is bilingual, so you can speak in both languages [. . .]. If you know the languages they speak, they can speak to you in their own language, inviting them and bringing other people together so that they can also speak to them and they. . . feel confident that here they help and that they can help. (Interview XXIV, District 4, New York City)

Well, trying to have the ads in their languages, which is a bit difficult, but is the best way to join the voices of the international population. Trying to get the ads in as many languages as possible. (Interview XXV, District 5, New York City)

In the school context of Granada, different strategies and proposals were suggested to facilitate the building of bridges; and for increasing the participation and involvement of immigrant parents in the actions of PA/PTAs with the aim of improving the school, but also of enriching the intercultural education of the children and the school curriculum. Some of these suggestions included:

- *Languages awareness*: training in the school language (in this case Spanish) for those who need it.
- *Attendance*: to know how to approach families and see how they would like to participate, the use of ICT, flexibility of schedules, giving more responsibility to foreign families and carrying out activities with which they can relate or identify.

- *Cultural Welcoming Environment (CWE)*: to know more about their culture, through the teaching staff and the promotion of immigrant families' values, including respect, effort and work.

I think that by calling them more specifically. If it is known that someone has arrived new, you can inform them about the activities and ask them to participate. It is about customizing the call to them. This is a good way, but sometimes we do it and sometimes we do not. You have to meet them. (Interview I, District Albaicín, Granada)

I think there should be more knowledge of both. Putting both cultures in the position of the other to understand us a little better, I think it should be like this. (Interview V, District Chana, Granada)

The above insights expanded our knowledge and helped us to characterize the 'challenges' that PA/PTAs leaders and schools face in New York City and Granada schools. In the following section we provide a discussion of these findings, centred on our two main research objectives and the relevant literature.

Discussion and conclusion

This study aimed to contribute new insights with a description of immigrant families' participation in PA/PTA in two different national contexts (Objective 1) and to bring new insights from the views of PA/PTA leaders about how to engage and improve the participation of 'hard-to-reach', immigrant families in schools (Objective 2).

Regarding the first objective, although all PA/PTAs leaders in both contexts think that the participation of 'hard-to-reach' families, in our case immigrant families, has a positive effect on the entire educational community, we found that many families do not participate in the school either in an active way or in general. In many cases, they do not have sufficient information about this possibility and they do not fully understand how to get involved, as some of the narratives of PA/PTAs leaders indicated. According to an earlier study conducted by one of the authors (Evangelou et al. 2013), families who appear hard to reach simply may lack the knowledge of the service that is needed because the service providers are not making appreciate provision to overcome these families access to barriers. Likewise, our findings reveal that families do not participate because they lack information and/or could not fully understand how to become involved.

The integration of families' cultural resources into the school climate is an effective means of increasing students' engagement and learning (Lucas, Henze, and Donato 1990; Nieto 2002), and is related to higher parental involvement with their children's school (Delgado-Gaitan 2004; Mercado and Moll 2000). Participating in PA/PTAs enables immigrant parents to have a voice in the daily life of their children's school. Moreover, it is a benefit not only for these families (as they have a space to meet other parents and to create networking between them and other parents even with parents from different schools) but also for the entire educational community. It is the shared space around children, parents, teachers and staff members that allows PA/PTAs to build a social capital and 'civic engagement' around education (López Castellano, García-Quero, and García-Carmona 2018).

Developmental/ecological theory continues to provide a relevant conceptual framework to guide empirical enquiry into the family-school partnerships (Christenson and Sheridan 2001), as we are focused not only on PA/PTA membership, but also much more. To maximize opportunities to learn through the school-family partnership, we believe in an association as a space of growing together, a space that enables families with different backgrounds to share experiences about one of the most important issues in their lives: the education of their children. The quality and quantity of interactions between a parent and a school contribute to the formation of their relationship, but taking into account that the whole is greater than the sum of the parts is necessary.

The findings contribute new insights to ecological systems; specifically the component that assumes that parents and teachers must work together towards a uniform socialization and education of the child. This perspective has assumed all parents share the same human and social capital as well as a similar culture or understanding of the types and forms of participation that is expected of them by schools in the new, host society. Our findings reveal that some immigrant parents lack these resources, especially parents who import low levels of human and social capital and that PA/PTAs are key in the education and resocialization of these parents but also of native born parents with similarly limited resources.

In this sense, we need committed PA/PTAs leaders and schools whose efforts are channelled into working with parents, no matter how initially 'hard-to-reach' they are. They can pay dividends to the school in the long run, as parents who are supportive can have a positive impact on their child's learning, behaviour and attendance (Campbell 2011). In the interviews, leaders demonstrated that there are still barriers that impede these families from being part of the PA/PTA. Although fortunately there are schools with a number of immigrant parents being part of the PA/PTA executive board, there are still many schools where the participation of these parents is very low. Parents, especially those with lower education levels, may feel less effective in their attempts to help their children in school-related matters (Downer and Mendez 2005; Eccles and Harold 1993; Hoover-Dempsey and Sandler 1997), which could be an explanation for reduced parental involvement over time (Downer and Mayers 2010).

It arises as an opportunity for the PA/PTAs leaders and the personnel of the school because, when parents feel that they are satisfying their parental responsibilities and their efforts are benefiting their children, they are more likely to be involved in their children's schooling (Hoover-Dempsey et al. 2005). PA/PTAs leaders need to implement different measures that encourage families to take part in their associations from intercultural perspectives that underline the importance of understanding both the immigrant and the host nation's cultures in achieving a strong and constructive parent-school connection (García-Carmona 2014).

Concerning the second objective, we need to reflect on effective strategies that give 'hard-to-reach' families the opportunity to be more involved, and that also allow the school to 'reach' them. It is always a double direction intervention between school and families. PA/PTAs leaders need to be committed to identifying the 'hard-to-reach' parents and to persist in including them in their child's education for the benefit of their children, the school and the community as a whole (Campbell 2011). They need to make a special call to all these families and to listen to them. For this purpose, PA/PTAs

leaders need to focus both within and beyond the school gates, as in the home and family environments.

Although teachers are a key piece of the puzzle, they cannot close the achievement gap alone (Delpit 1988; Ladson-Billings 2006; LaRocque, Kleiman, and Darling 2011), and new strategies involving the community need to be implemented (Barrett 2008). In this sense, PA/PTAs leaders play an important role, as they can create a welcoming environment that promotes the participation of parents. Therefore, when parents perceive that their children and/or their child's school leaders want them involved, their participation is more likely to increase (Anderson and Minke 2007).

Thus, it is up to school leaders (including PA/PTAs leaders, school leadership teams, educational government, etc.) to initiate communication in an inclusive and respectful manner in order to learn rather than telling how best to foster and increase parent involvement (Watson and Bogotch 2015). Consequently, schools need to place parental engagement at the centre rather than at the periphery of all that they do (Harris and Goodall 2007).

We would suggest that schools work holistically with parents the socialization and education. One of the main strategies is to provide bilingual information about school practices, curriculum and level of participation expected of parents. As one of the main strategies suggested by the insights among PA/PTAs, the dissemination of information is the most important factor enabling parents to participate in schools. The translation of all documents and notices is the first step in making the school information accessible to all parents. The language is the main channel of communication and without this bridging real involvement is not possible. Students, but also families, need to feel that the school is their space and community.

A characteristic of effective interventions is that they are culturally appropriate to individual families and sensitive to their needs (Johnson 2011; Sure Start 2001). In this sense, strategies that we can use to help to get parents involved in the school, and to overcome barriers to access, include: encouraging social interaction and trusting relationships; presenting a welcoming school; creating an accessible and inclusive environment; providing information and knowledge (Evangelou et al. 2017) to parents about volunteering in the classroom; planning regular family events; and holding personal meetings with the 'harder-to-reach' families.

Our findings indicate that it is also essential that the school and consequently the PA/PTA promotes the knowledge of different cultures and integrates them into the school curriculum. This strategy should be based on the proportion of different cultures of persons that form the school community and their views. It is not only the celebration of a particular 'intercultural event' in a specific day, but also the deep and personal knowledge of this group's identity in their culture and in the culture of the host school, that is the sum of all their identities. In this regard, both Granada and New York City are working on this aspect, but there is still a long way to close the gap of participation of immigrant families in their schools.

Parents also need flexibility in the possibilities of involvement. In this sense, ICT offers different options (sending of emails or text messages, posting important information on PA/PTA webpages, communication through social networks, etc.) that allow parents to be updated about important or key information in the education of their children. PA/PTAs also need to become more aware of the benefits but also the liabilities of communication through the Internet given the limitations and greater challenges faced by immigrant

families, especially those of low socioeconomic status. PA/PTAs should take this aspect into account as they broadcast their meetings via the Internet and other Internet-based forums, chats and other social media platforms. PA/PTAs leaders stand out to benefit from and also contribute to social change in the use of new channels of communication between schools and families but also in the mode in which this communication is organized towards improving the participation of a higher number of families in their PA/PTA.

Finally, a consistent message to emerge from the study is that complex issues, like how to get 'hard-to-reach' parents involved in schools, need complex solutions, which in turn need time to implement. Additionally, it is clear that schools need to develop a diversity of support provision in order to meet the varying needs of families. This point should be taken into account in order to promote a more open and accessible school for everyone that is, an inclusive school (Ainscow 2005). Family participation should be encouraged by the educational institution, with the intention of creating new strategies to help families to feel that they play an important part in their children's educational process and in the school community.

Note

1. In this study, the terms 'family' and 'parents' describe mothers, fathers, caregivers and other adults who are responsible for the care of a child, including family members, friends and non-kin caregivers.

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